

Microplastic load and distribution in the respiratory and digestive systems of some commercial fish species in the southwestern coast of Bangladesh

Modhuparna Dey¹, Adiba Mosharraf², Ferdousi Begum^{1*}, Mohammad Mahbubur Rahman³, Md. Abu Bin Hasan Susan⁴

¹ Bangladesh Maritime University, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh

² Institute of Water Modelling, Dhaka-1230, Bangladesh

³ Bangladesh Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (BCSIR), Dhaka-1205, Bangladesh

⁴ University of Dhaka, Dhaka-1000, Bangladesh

*Corresponding author: ferdousi.chem@bmu.edu.bd

DOI:

Article Info

Keywords

Microplastic
Ingestion
Commercial Fish
Gills & Gastrointestinal Tracts
Kuakata
Bay of Bengal

Article History

Received 30 July 2025

Accepted 22 November 2025

Published 08 December 2025

Copyright 2025@BJO. Published by
Bangladesh Oceanographic Research Institute

Abstract

Microplastic (MP) pollution poses a growing threat to marine ecosystems and human health, particularly in coastal regions with intense fishing and commercial activities. This study investigated the occurrence, characteristics, and sources of MPs in three commercially important fish species, *Otolithoides pama* (Poa), *Glossogobius giuris* (Bele), and *Euthynnus affinis* (Little Tuna), collected from the Kuakata coast in the northern Bay of Bengal (BoB). A total of six individuals (two per species) were analyzed to provide a baseline understanding of MP contamination. MPs were identified in both gills and gastrointestinal tracts (GITs) using microscopy and characterized by size, color, shape, and polymer type. Descriptive statistical analysis revealed that the mean MP abundance was highest in *G. giuris* (0.54 ± 0.08 particles g^{-1}), followed by *O. pama* (0.18 ± 0.03 particles g^{-1}) and *E. affinis* (0.018 ± 0.005 particles g^{-1}). Most MPs were small (0.05-0.25 mm) transparent fibers, likely derived from fishing gear and textile sources. Ten polymer types were identified using Attenuated Total Reflectance Fourier Transform Infrared (ATR-FTIR) spectroscopy, where nylon, polystyrene (PS), and polyvinyl chloride (PVC) were most prevalent, indicating multiple pollution sources such as fishing activities, packaging materials, and household waste. Exploratory correlation analysis suggested a negative association between fish size and MP load ($r = -0.84$ to -0.94). Although limited by a small sample size, exploratory PCA and HCA revealed species- and tissue-specific patterns, indicating multiple pollution sources. The findings serve as an initial baseline for MP contamination in coastal fish from Bangladesh and underscoring the need for expanded, seasonally replicated monitoring and improved plastic waste management to safeguard aquatic biodiversity and food safety; however, the study's limitations, including a relatively small sample size and the omission of flesh (muscle tissue) analysis for MP contamination, mean the reported extent of the problem and potential risk to human consumers may be underestimated.

1. Introduction

Microplastics (MPs) pollution has become a major environmental issue, especially in densely populated coastal areas where human activities like fishing and commercial operations increase contamination (Kushwaha et al., 2024; Arat, 2024). The fisheries sector of Bangladesh, employing around 18 million people, is among the largest globally and contributes about 3.5% to the national GDP, meeting 60% of the animal protein demand of the country (Tamang et al., 2023). Fish, though a smaller dietary component, is a key source of omega-3 fatty acids like eicosatetraenoic acid (EPA) that helps to prevent coronary diseases, arrhythmias, thrombosis, lowers triglyceride levels, and may reduce premature delivery risks (Hussain & Hoq, 2010; Tamang et al., 2023) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA), which are essential for brain and heart health (Domingo et al., 2007). Additionally, fish provides high-quality protein, iodine, vitamins, and minerals. The artisanal fishing sector also supports rural livelihoods and food security. However, pollution from MPs poses growing threats to marine ecosystems and human health, endangering this vital sector.

Plastic materials are classified into five size groups: megaplastics (>1 m), macroplastics (1 m-25 mm), mesoplastics (25-5 mm), microplastics (<5 mm), and nanoplastics (<1 μ m) (Uhrin et al., 2019). MPs and nanoplastics are the most concerning due to their widespread presence in marine environments, coming from the breakdown of larger plastics by sunlight and weather (Eriksen et al., 2014) or being made directly at small sizes, like pellets. MP pollution in marine fish has emerged as a critical environmental issue, with widespread contamination observed across species, habitats, and regions. Globally, studies have documented MP contamination in fish from both marine and freshwater environments. In the Northeast Atlantic, Lusher et al. (2013) found that 36.5% of sampled fish had ingested plastic particles, with fibers being the most common type. Similarly, a study in the Mediterranean Sea revealed MPs in 18 different fish species, highlighting regional pollution from tourism and maritime activities (Avio et al., 2015). In Arctic waters, even remote species like polar cod have shown MP presence, demonstrating the global dispersion of MPs via ocean currents and atmospheric transport (Kühn et al., 2018). However, in Southeast Asia, a known hotspot of plastic pollution, MPs were found in 55% of fish from Indonesia and 28% from the Philippines, primarily due to poor waste management systems (Rochman et al., 2013). Freshwater ecosystems are also affected. Su et al. (2019) reported MPs in over 90% of fish from China's Yangtze River, indicating the severity of inland pollution.

MP contamination in aquatic ecosystems is a global crisis, driven by human activities and spread by natural forces like wind, rivers, and ocean currents, impacting nearly 800 marine species worldwide (Xu et al., 2018; Worm et al., 2017). Fish are critical vectors for MPs, transferring them through the food chain to humans, a risk supported by growing evidence of MPs within human tissues (Li et al., 2024; Yarahmadi et al., 2024). Upon ingestion, MPs can cause physical harm, blockages, and leach toxic chemicals into fish

tissues, posing a threat to predators (Walkinshaw et al., 2020; Bucci et al., 2020). The characteristics of ingested MPs are well-documented; they are predominantly less than 1 mm in size, with fibrous white and blue fragments of polymers like polyethylene (PE), polyurethane (PU), and polypropylene (PP) being most common, originating from fishing gear, ocean currents, and atmospheric deposition (Pan et al., 2021; Peng et al., 2018; Islam et al., 2022; Toha et al., 2024). Ingestion dynamics are influenced by ecology, as carnivorous fish typically ingest fewer MPs than herbivorous or omnivorous fish, and demersal species exhibit higher loads than pelagic fish due to greater sediment interaction, while midwater fish show lower gill concentrations (Pan et al., 2021; Srisiri et al., 2024; Islam et al., 2025). MPs are consistently found in both the gastrointestinal tracts (GITs) and gills, with gills often showing higher concentrations due to continuous water filtration, highlighting their role as a primary entry route (Yona et al., 2020). Spatial variability is significant, as seen in reef fish from Papua, where Liki Island had the highest contamination (Yona et al., 2020), and the relationship with fish size remains complex, with some studies finding no correlation and others suggesting larger fish may contain fewer MPs (Yona et al., 2020; Dey et al., 2025a). In Bangladesh, research confirms a severe and widespread issue (Tamim et al., 2025; Haque et al., 2023; Toha et al., 2024), with initial studies in rivers like the Buriganga finding MPs in all fish examined (Haque et al., 2023). Coastal studies in the Bay of Bengal (BoB) reveal pervasive contamination, with one pivotal study reporting MPs in 100% of marine fish samples with an average abundance of 12.7 ± 2.8 particles per individual (Hossain et al., 2023), while the southwestern coast near Kuakata showed even higher levels at 15.2 ± 3.1 items per individual (Parvin et al., 2022). Advanced methodologies have detected MPs in 93.75% of Bangladeshi fish samples, collectively underscoring that coastal fish, a crucial food source, are significant vectors for MPs, posing a direct and quantified risk to food safety and public health in the region (Siddique et al., 2025; Rahman et al., 2025).

Although several studies have documented MP contamination in marine fish from Bangladesh and the northern BoB, they primarily focused on total MP abundance or general occurrence in commercial species such as *E. affinis* (Little Tuna) (Hossain et al., 2023; Sultana et al., 2024; Islam et al., 2025). However, no published research to date has examined organ-specific MP accumulation in *O. pama* (Poa) and *G. giuris* (Bele), two widely consumed and economically significant species inhabiting the southwestern coastal waters. Understanding the distribution of MPs between gills and GITs in these fishes (*O. pama*, *G. giuris*, and *E. affinis*) is essential, as it provides perceptions into potential exposure routes and biological uptake mechanisms that remain unexplored in the Bangladeshi context. Therefore, this study serves as a baseline investigation of organ-level MP contamination in these species, integrating both physical characterization (size, shape, color) and polymer identification through ATR-FTIR analysis. Furthermore, exploratory multivariate analyses (PCA and HCA) were applied to visualize poly

mer source patterns and species-specific accumulation tendencies. The outcomes aim to fill a critical knowledge gap in national MP research and to establish a foundation for future, larger-scale ecological and food safety assessments in the coastal waters of Bangladesh.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Area and Sample Collection

Figure 1 shows the geographical coordinates of the sampling station of the Kuakata Alipur Bazar from where the fish species were collected, and the pictures of the fish. A total of 6 individual fish, 2 per species, were collected from a seashore fish market, Alipur Bazar in Kuakata, Bangladesh, during February 2024, caught by local fishermen in the north BoB. The fishes are classified as benthopelagic species: *Otolithoides pama*, *Glossogobius giuris*, and pelagic-neritic species: *Euthynnus affinis* shown in Table 1. These species were selected due to their different habitat, availability throughout the year, and economic importance (www.fishbase.org). As this was a baseline study, market-sourced specimens were used to provide an initial indication of MPs contamination in commonly consumed fish. To minimize potential secondary contamination, each specimen was wrapped in aluminum foil, transported in ice boxes (-20 °C), and thoroughly rinsed with pre-filtered distilled water prior to dissection, following the recommendations of Lusher et al. (2013). The body length (cm) and weight (g) of each fish were recorded. Each fish was then opened on a wood tray, scissors, a scalpel, and forceps were used to remove the gills and GITs carefully, and then transferred to a Petri dish and weighed (g). Finally, the GITs were placed in a 500 mL glass beaker for the extraction of MPs and covered with aluminum foil to minimize the risk of contamination.

Figure 1: Geographical coordinates of the sampling station of the Kuakata Alipur Bazar, from where the fish species were collected (left). Three types of collected fish species: (a) *O. pama*, (b) *G. giuris*, and (c) *E. affinis* (right).

2.2. Extraction of Microplastics

MPs from the gills and GITs of different fish were extracted using the peroxide oxidation based digestion method, slightly modified described in the NOAA procedure (Masura et al., 2015). Organic matter was digested using 10% KOH at 60 °C for 1 hour, followed by 5 mL H₂O₂ and 30 minutes of rotation, then left for 3 days for complete digestion. The digested solution was sieved (125 µm mesh), and the residues were transferred to clean 500 mL beakers. Further oxidation with 0.05 M Fe (II) and 30% H₂O₂ was performed at 70 °C until bubbling stopped, with additional H₂O₂ added if needed. For density separation, NaCl (36 g per beaker) was dissolved at 75 °C to float MPs, and the solution was left in a separatory funnel for 24 hours. The filtrate and backwashed residues were vacuum-filtered using glass microfiber filters (1.0 µm, 47 mm). Filters were stored in glass petri dishes, covered with aluminum foil, and air-dried for further analysis. All washing solutions were pre-filtered to minimize MP contamination. The modification in concentration and duration was performed to simultaneously improve organic matter breakdown and prevent the thermal degradation of microfibers, thus ensuring accurate MP recovery. Furthermore, the decision to pursue this modification was influenced by the cost and unavailability of density-increasing elements (mentioned by NOAA protocols) in the lab, which presented an additional, practical reason for adopting the adapted method.

2.3. Quantification and Characterization of Microplastics

MPs were identified visually under a binocular microscope (Optika Digital Microscope with Camera and Tablet, Model: B-290TB microscope, Italy). Each of the MPs was counted, adjusting the magnification from 10x to 100x.

Figure 2: Flow diagram of the examination of MPs contamination in the gills and GITs of Poa, Bele, and Little Tuna fish.

The number, color, shape, and size of MPs in each fish species were recorded, and the abundance of MPs was calculated as the number of particles per fish species, individuals, body weight, and GITs, along with the statistical analysis of variances (Table 1). The polymer types present in MPs were identified by Attenuated Total Reflection Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR) (FTIR-4600, JASCO Inc., Tokyo, Japan), wave number ranging from 4000 to 550 cm^{-1} with a spectral resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . Background cleaning was completed before each particle measurement. A flow diagram of the examination of MPs contamination in the gills and GITs of collected fish is represented in Figure 2.

2.4. Quality Assurance and Quality Control

Fish dissection and separation of the gills and GITs were done inside a clean tray, and the GITs were placed in a petri dish and covered to prevent contamination. Cotton cloths, latex gloves, glassware, and metalware were used in the laboratory. All the glassware, dissection tools, and filtration units were rinsed three times with deionized water. One blank sample without fish gill and GIT was prepared following the same procedure to correct the potential procedural contamination, if any. Since all the fish were collected from fishermen in an open fish market, there were no controls over MP contamination from the time of being harvested to their arrival at the market. As a result, each fish sample was cleaned with distilled water to remove any externally attached plastic.

2.5. Statistical Analysis

To comprehensively assess MP contamination, including potential sources and their relationship with fish morphology, a multi-faceted statistical approach was employed. Descriptive statistics, including mean, median, maximum values, skewness, standard deviation, variance, and kurtosis, were first calculated for all MP characteristics as well as for the number of MPs found in various fish compartments (overall, gills, and GITs). This provided an initial understanding of the central tendency and the extreme values of MP occurrence. To identify underlying patterns and potential sources of MP contamination, exploratory PCA was utilized as a dimensionality reduction technique on the detailed MP characteristics. PCA helped condense complex MP profiles into principal components, with component loadings guiding the interpretation of key source indicators. Following this, HCA was performed on the derived principal components or raw MP characteristic data to group fish samples or locations based on similarities in their MP contamination profiles, thus revealing potential common pollution origins. Finally, to investigate the relationship between MP distribution and fish size, Pearson correlation analysis was conducted. This evaluated the linear association between the number of MPs (total, gill, and GIT counts) and key fish morphological parameters, specifically total body weight and total length, providing insights into whether larger or heavier fish were more prone to MP accumulation. Statistical analysis was performed using Microsoft Excel 2019 and R Studio (with R version 3.5.1, www.rstudio.com), and figures were generated using ggplot2 (version 3.1.0).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Characteristics of the Collected Fish

Morphological measurements of each fish sample, such as total length, fork length, and the wet weight of the sample fish (n=3), were carried out with standard deviation. Table 1 presents data on three fish species: *O. pama*, *G. giuris*, and *E. affinis*, detailing their habitats, average total length, average wet weight, average gill wet weight, average GIT wet weight, and average number of MPs per gram in general, in gills, and in the GITs. *O. pama* inhabits freshwater, brackish, and marine environments, with an average total length and wet weight of 26.50 ± 0.10 cm and 145.83 ± 11.87 g, respectively. Its average gill wet weight was 1.586 ± 0.19 g, and its average GIT wet weight was 3.18 ± 0.39 g. *G. giuris*, is considerably smaller, measuring 18.50 ± 1.41 cm in average total length and weighing 67.88 ± 6.64 g on average. Its gill and GIT wet weights were notably lower, at 0.07 ± 0.01 g and 0.17 ± 0.06 g, respectively. In contrast, *E. affinis* is a large marine species, with an average total length of 45.50 ± 0.71 cm and a substantial average wet weight of 1082.13 ± 48.17 g. Correspondingly, its average gill wet weight was 37.19 ± 11.42 g, and its average GIT wet weight was 59.74 ± 16.23 g, reflecting its much larger overall size.

Table 1: Morphological characteristics of collected fish samples with the average distribution of MPs in fish samples, particularly in gills and GITs.

Fish Species	Local Name	Habitats	Avg Total Length (cm)	Avg Wet Wt. (g)	Avg Gill Wet Wt. (g)	Avg GIT Wet Wt. (g)	Avg No. of MPs (per g)	Avg No. of MPs in Gill (per g)	Avg No. of MPs in GIT (per g)
<i>O. pama</i>	Poa	Freshwater, Brackish and Marine	26.50 ± 0.10	145.83 ± 11.87	1.58 ± 0.19	3.18 ± 0.39	0.18 ± 0.02	15.13 ± 2.67	9.44 ± 0.667
<i>G. giuris</i>	Bele		18.50 ± 1.41	67.88 ± 6.64	0.07 ± 0.01	0.17 ± 0.06	0.25 ± 0.01	2.77 ± 0.14	5.59 ± 0.36
<i>E. affinis</i>	Little Tuna	Marine	45.50 ± 0.71	1082.13 ± 48.17	37.19 ± 11.42	59.74 ± 16.23	0.13 ± 0.02	0.63 ± 0.09	0.27 ± 0.08

Figure 3: Microscopic observation and identification of different colors, shapes, and lengths of MPs. (a-c) fiber, (d-f) fragment, (g-i) foam, and (j-l) line.

3.2. Identification of Microplastics

Microscopic observations revealed diverse MP characteristics, varying in color, shape, and length (Figure 3 & 4). The *G. giuris* exhibited the highest overall proportionate burden of MPs, with the gills of the Bele fish compartment accounting for the single largest fraction at 25% of the total count. This was closely followed by the digestive tracts of *G. giuris*, contributing 19%, and *O. pama*, accounting for 18%. The respiratory tissues of *O. pama* and *E. affinis* each contributed an equal, moderate proportion of 14%. Notably, the lowest proportion of total MPs was observed in the digestive tract of the largest species, *E. affinis*, at 10%. These findings clearly demonstrate a preferential accumulation of MPs in the gills and GITs tissues of *G. giuris* (44% combined) compared to the other two species.

Figure 4: Proportionate distribution of total MP particles across fish species and tissues. The chart illustrates the percentage contribution of MPs found in the gills and GITs of *pama* (Poa), *G. giuris* (Bele), and *E. affinis* (Little Tuna).

3.3. Distribution of Length, Color, and Polymer Type

3.3.1. Length

Figure 5 illustrates that the analysis of MP length across the three fish species: *O. pama*, *G. giuris*, and *E. affinis* reveals that the median size of MPs is consistently small and similar (below 0.01 mm) in both the gills and GITs tissues. For the vast majority of particles (the middle 50%), the length spans a narrow range, typically between 0.02 mm and 0.15 mm. However, despite the similar median sizes, the largest MPs were found as outliers in the gills tissues, with the Bele exhibiting the single largest particle at nearly 1.0 mm, followed by outliers in the Poa (up to 0.5 mm) and Tuna (up to approx 0.4 mm in both tissues), indicating that while small particles dominate the count, much larger particles are also being captured, predominantly by the gills.

Figure 5: Length distribution with standard deviation of MPs in gills (green colour) and GITs (orange colour) of Poa, Bele, and Little Tuna fish.

3.3.2. Colors

Seven colors (transparent, brown, red, blue, black, green, and purple) of MPs were identified in both the gills and GITs of fish, as shown in Figure 6 (left). Transparent MPs consistently emerged as the most dominant color across nearly all samples, particularly in the gills of Bele (46 %), the GIT of Poa (34 %), and the GITs of Bele (29 %). This dominance may be attributed to the widespread use of clear plastic products such as packaging films, fishing lines, and plastic bags, which are prone to degradation and fragmentation in aquatic environments (Dimassi et al., 2022). Brown MPs showed a notable presence in the gills of Little Tuna and Poa (12 %), likely originating from degraded colored plastics or sediment-associated particles (Yousuf et al., 2025). Blue MPs were also consistently detected, peaking at 15 % in the gills of Bele, possibly reflecting the frequent use of blue fishing nets, ropes, or synthetic fabrics in coastal areas. In contrast, Red, Black, Green, and Purple MPs appeared in much smaller proportions, suggesting lower environmental prevalence or reduced visibility and ingestion likelihood due to their distinct coloration or particle density (Hossain et al., 2024).

3.3.3. Types

Five types of MPs (fiber, fragment, foam, line, and pellet) were detected in the gills and GITs of fish, as shown in Figure 6 (right). Among them, fiber was the most dominant type across nearly all categories, with especially high proportions in the gills of Bele (62 %), the GIT of Poa (55 %), and the GITs of Bele (53 %). This dominance likely stems

from the extensive use of synthetic textiles, fishing gear, and ropes, which release fibers into aquatic environments through washing, wear, and degradation (Jolaosho et al., 2025). Line was ranked as the second most common type, particularly in gills samples such as Little Tuna (21 %) and Bele (14 %), which may be linked to the breakdown of fishing lines or nets commonly used in coastal and riverine fishing. Fragment showed more limited representation, with its highest presence in the gills of Poa (12 %), likely originating from the breakdown of rigid plastic particles like containers or packaging. Meanwhile, foam and pellet appeared only in trace amounts or were absent entirely, possibly due to their lower usage near the sampling zones or their tendency to float and accumulate in surface water rather than being ingested by demersal or benthopelagic fish.

Figure 6: Distribution of color (left) and distribution of shape (right) of Poa, Bele, and Little Tuna fish.

3.4. Chemical Composition

Chemical structures of the polymers present in the observed MPs were analyzed using ATR-FTIR spectroscopy, which identified distinct absorption bands corresponding to ten polymer types found in the gills and GITs of fish collected from Kuakata. The identified polymers included high-density polyethylene (HDPE), low-density polyethylene (LDPE), polypropylene (PP), polystyrene (PS), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), polyurethane (PU), nylon, ethylene-vinyl acetate (EVA), polycarbonate (PC), and polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE), as confirmed by characteristic wavelength ranges and reference data from Lithner et al. (2011) (Figure 7).

Figure 7: ATR-FTIR spectra of identified polymers in the observed MPs, (a) HDPE, (b) LDPE, (c) PP, (d) PS, (e) PVC, (f) PU, (g) Nylon, (h) EVA, (i) PC, and (j) PTFE.

In this study, HDPE and LDPE showed prominent bands between 2921-2931 cm⁻¹ and 715-740 cm⁻¹, while EVA exhibited peaks within 1000-1021 cm⁻¹ and 2855-2922 cm⁻¹. Nylon displayed multiple absorption bands at 1367, 1539-1684, and 2850-3372 cm⁻¹, and PP revealed distinctive peaks between 797-1167 cm⁻¹ and 2926-2943 cm⁻¹. PS was identified by bands at 1027-1031 cm⁻¹, 2853 cm⁻¹, and 3028 cm⁻¹, whereas PU showed strong peaks between 1218-1831 cm⁻¹. PC exhibited characteristic signals at 1000-1509 cm⁻¹ and 2973 cm⁻¹, PVC within 1052-1434 cm⁻¹, and PTFE between 654-1206 cm⁻¹. The diversity of these spectral bands indicates the widespread presence of synthetic materials

originating from various anthropogenic sources. HDPE, LDPE, and PP likely derive from packaging and domestic waste (Silva et al., 2023), PS and PVC from insulation and construction materials, nylon and EVA from fishing gear and footwear (Zaman et al., 2024), PU and PC from foams, coatings, and electronics, and PTFE from industrial and household products. The variety of polymers detected reflects multiple contamination pathways, demonstrating the extensive and complex infiltration of plastic pollutants into the aquatic environment and their subsequent accumulation in fish tissues (Hassan & Ibrahim, 2025).

3.5. Comparison of Microplastics between Gills and GITs

The average percentage of polymer types found in the gills and GITs of the collected fish samples, based on data from Lithner et al., (2011), is shown in Figure 8. The analysis revealed that nylon was the most frequently occurring polymer in both organs, accounting for 13.63 % in gills and 32.35 % in GITs. This high prevalence of nylon likely originates from fishing-related activities, as it is a primary component of fishing nets, lines, and ropes, which are widely used in coastal areas like Kuakata (Hossain et al., 2024). The breakdown and loss of this equipment into aquatic systems can lead to significant nylon contamination. In the gills, the next most common polymers were PS (11.36 %), PVC (9.09 %), PC (6.81 %), and EVA (4.54 %). These materials are often used in food packaging, household goods, electronic devices, and footwear, suggesting contributions from domestic waste and shoreline litter. In the GITs, the order of polymer presence followed Nylon (32.35 %) > PS (14.70 %) > PVC (5.88 %) > PTFE (2.94 %). Higher occurrence of PS and PVC in the GITs may be due to their resemblance to natural food particles in size and texture, making them more likely to be ingested. Minor presence of PTFE indicates possible input from industrial or household sources.

Figure 8: Average percentage of polymer types found in the gills and GITs of the collected fish samples: Poa, Bele, and Little Tuna fish.

3.6. Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Among the examined fish species, clear interspecific variations in MP accumulation were observed (Table 1). *G. giuris* exhibited the highest overall MP concentration (0.54 ± 0.08 particles/g), with a notably greater load in the gills (2.77 ± 0.14 particles/g) than in the GIT (0.59 ± 0.36 particles/g), suggesting higher exposure through respiration due to its benthic habitat and feeding behavior. *O. pama* showed a moderate MP concentration (0.18 ± 0.03 particles/g), with the highest accumulation in the GIT (0.94 ± 0.67 particles/g), followed by the gills (1.51 ± 0.27 particles/g), indicating ingestion as the dominant pathway of MP uptake. In contrast, *E. affinis*, the largest species analyzed, contained the lowest MP burden (0.02 ± 0.01 particles/g), reflecting minimal accumulation in both gills (0.63 ± 0.09 particles/g) and GIT (0.27 ± 0.08 particles/g), which may be attributed to its pelagic feeding habits or efficient elimination mechanisms. Statistical descriptors in Table 2 further supported these trends, as gills generally retained slightly higher MP levels than the GIT across all species. The variability in MP distribution was greatest in Bele gills, which exhibited the highest standard deviation (0.1487), variance (0.0221), and strong positive skewness (4.81) with elevated kurtosis (24.36), indicating occasional extreme accumulations. In contrast, Poa gut samples showed near-normal distributions (skewness = 0.91; kurtosis = 0.31). Collectively, these findings indicate that gills tend to accumulate more MPs than the gut, with Bele demonstrating the most pronounced and irregular MP deposition, likely due to species-specific feeding ecology and environmental exposure patterns.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of microplastic abundance in the gills and GITs of *O. pama*, *G. giuris* and *E. affinis*, including mean, median, standard deviation, variance, minimum, maximum, skewness, and kurtosis.

Sample ID	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Variance	Min	Max	Skewness	Kurtosis
Poa Gill	0.1005	0.0615	0.1033	0.0107	0.005	0.486	1.8739	3.3263
Poa Gut	0.0968	0.0850	0.0646	0.0042	0.003	0.264	0.9088	0.3112
Bele Gill	0.0990	0.0690	0.1487	0.0221	0.007	0.990	4.8097	24.3640
Bele Gut	0.0732	0.0540	0.0649	0.0042	0.011	0.444	3.3061	14.9764
Tuna Gill	0.0885	0.0500	0.0867	0.0075	0.005	0.398	1.7695	2.7700
Tuna Gut	0.0841	0.0680	0.0665	0.0044	0.014	0.342	2.3849	6.3613

3.7. Pearson Correlation

A strong negative correlation was observed between MP count and all fish morphological parameters (fish weight, standard length, fork length, total length, gill weight, and gut weight) using Pearson correlation with coefficients ranging from -0.84 to -0.94. In contrast, red areas reflect strong positive correlations among the size-related variables (Figure 9). The inverse relationship suggests that larger, heavier fish tend to carry fewer MPs, possibly due to their higher trophic position, better-developed elimination mechanisms, or inhabiting less polluted areas. Growth dilution and higher mortality in smaller, more contaminated fish may also contribute. These results underscore the complex dynamics

of MP accumulation and call for deeper ecological and physiological investigation.

Figure 9: Pearson correlation between the morphological parameters of the fish sample and the number of MPs found in the fish sample (confidence level 95 %).

3.8. Principal Component Analysis

PCA of the results highlights that PC1 and PC2 together account for approximately 70.34 % of the variance, with PC1 contributing 37.50 % and PC2 contributing 32.84 % (Figure 10a). These two components capture the majority of the variance, providing insight into the structure of the data. PC1 primarily differentiates between polymers like nylon, PTFE, and PVC (positive loadings) along with EVA, HDPE, and LDPE (negative loadings), suggesting distinct sources: the latter group points towards pervasive packaging and single-use plastics, while the former might indicate industrial or specialized consumer product origins. PC2, on the other hand, highlights the prevalence of PU, PS, and PP, indicating that significant contributions were from foams, synthetic materials, and various consumer goods. The combined analysis of these components and their strong loadings by specific polymer types allows us to infer the primary causes of MP pollution: widespread reliance on packaging and single-use plastics (HDPE, LDPE), the degradation of synthetic textiles and fibers (nylon, PTFE), the breakdown of foams and consumer products (PS, PU, PP, EVA), and the wear and tear of construction materials

(PVC) (Toha et al., 2024). This intricate mix of polymer types underscores that MP pollution is a complex issue driven by diverse anthropogenic sources, including consumer habits, waste management inefficiencies, and the inherent durability and eventual fragmentation of plastic products across various sectors.

Figure 10: (a) PCA and (b) HCA analysis to observe the source of MPs in Poa, Bele, and Little Tuna fish.

3.9. Hierarchical Cluster Analysis

The dendrogram from the HCA (Figure 10b) visually elucidates the varying MP profiles across different fish species and their tissues. It reveals a close clustering of the GIT of Little Tuna with the GIT of Poa and the gills of Poa, indicating that these fish, or at least these specific tissues, are exposed to or accumulate similar types of MPs, likely due to shared feeding grounds or comparable diets. This implies that if their environments are rich in commonly found polymers such as HD/LD-PE, which is commonly used in packaging, or PS and PU, often found in foams and textiles, their MP profiles would reflect this similarity. Notably, within *O. pama*, the strong resemblance between MP characteristics of GIT and gill points towards either efficient systemic transfer or simultaneous exposure of both organs to similar environmental MP loads. Conversely, the striking isolation of the GIT of Bele and the gills of Bele, which were also distinct from each other, indicates that *G. giuris* encounters and accumulates a significantly different spectrum of MPs. This could stem from its unique habitat (e.g., bottom-feeding in a specific sediment type) or feeding strategy, which might expose it to different dominant polymer types, such as nylon, PTFE, or PVC. Overall, the HCA, when considered alongside data on polymer types, powerfully illustrates that MP accumulation patterns are highly influenced by species-specific ecological factors, including habitat, diet, and physiological differences in MP uptake and retention.

4. Conclusion

With rising plastic pollution threatening coastal ecosystems and seafood safety, this study offers a baseline evaluation of MP contamination in three economically and ecologically vital fish species: *O. pama*, *G. giuris*, and *E. affinis* from Kuakata, Bangladesh. The findings reveal that MPs were present in both gills and GITs of all examined species, indicating extensive contamination even in locally consumed fish. Among the species, *G. giuris* exhibited the highest MP burden, particularly in its gills, suggesting that benthic and demersal species are more exposed to MPs through sediment interaction and water filtration. Conversely, *E. affinis*, a pelagic species, showed the lowest MP load, likely due to its offshore habitat and feeding behavior. Microscopic and FTIR analyses confirmed diverse MP characteristics in terms of color, size, shape, and polymer type. Most particles were < 1 mm, predominantly fibrous and transparent, implying their origin from fishing gear, textiles, and packaging materials. Ten types of polymers were identified, with nylon, polyethylene (HDPE/LDPE), PP, and PS being the most abundant, reflecting multiple anthropogenic sources including fishing, household waste, and industrial discharges. Statistical analyses further revealed that gills generally contained more MPs than GITs, highlighting respiration as a major exposure route. The negative correlation between fish size and MP abundance indicates that smaller fish tend to accumulate higher MP loads, possibly due to habitat preference and feeding habits. Exploratory multivariate analyses (PCA and HCA) provided understandings into potential pollution sources, suggesting that MP contamination in these fish originates from a combination of packaging materials, fishing gear, textiles, and coastal waste. The clustering patterns also emphasized species-specific accumulation behaviors linked to ecological niches and feeding strategies. Collectively, this study confirms that MP contamination has already infiltrated the coastal food web of Bangladesh, posing potential ecological and human health risks. The results fill an important knowledge gap regarding organ-specific MP accumulation in local fish and establish a foundation for future large-scale monitoring, risk assessment, and policy interventions aimed at mitigating plastic pollution in the northern Bay of Bengal.

Acknowledgements

This research was partially performed under the thesis project of the B.Sc. in Fisheries. Additionally, the authors appreciate the Chemistry and Chemical Oceanography Lab, Bangladesh Maritime University (BMU), and the Analytical Division, Bangladesh Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (BCSIR) Laboratories for arranging this type of opportunity. Special thanks to Dr. Ferdousi Begum for funding this work. We also acknowledge the anonymous reviewers for their valuable comments.

References

- Arat, S. A. (2024). An overview of microplastic in marine waters: Sources, abundance, characteristics and negative effects on various marine organisms. *Desalination and Water Treatment*, 317, 100138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dwt.2024.100138>
- Avio, C. G., Gorbi, S., & Regoli, F. (2015). Experimental development of a new protocol for extraction and characterization of microplastics in fish tissues: First observation in commercial species from Adriatic Sea. *Marine Environmental Research*, 111, 18–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marenvres.2015.06.014>
- Bucci, K., Tulio, M., & Rochman, C. M. (2020). What is known and unknown about the effects of plastic pollution: A meta-analysis and systematic review. *Ecological Applications*, 30(2), e02044. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.2044>
- Dey, M., Begum, F., & Mosharraf, A. (2025a). Assessing microplastic contamination in Bele fish: Risks to aquatic ecosystems. Paper presented at the National Conference on Physics 2025, Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
- Dey, M., Begum, F., & Mosharraf, A. (2025b). Assessing microplastic contamination in Poa fish gills and guts: A threat to aquatic ecosystem. 10th International Conference on Water and Flood Management (ICWFM 2025), Dhaka, Bangladesh.
- Dimassi, S. N., Hahladakis, J. N., Daly Yahia, M. N., Ahmad, M. I., Sayadi, S., & Al-Ghouti M. A. (2022). Degradation-fragmentation of marine plastic waste and their environmental implications: A critical review. *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, 15(11), 104262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arabjc.2022.104262>
- Domingo, J. L., Bocio, A., Falcó, G., & Llobet, J. M. (2007). Benefits and risks of fish consumption. Part I. A quantitative analysis of the intake of omega-3 fatty acids and chemical contaminants. *Toxicology*, 230(2–3), 219–226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tox.2006.11.054>
- Eriksen, M., Lebreton, L. C. M., Carson, H. S., Thiel, M., Moore, C. J., Borerro, J. C., Galgani, F., Ryan, P. G., & Reisser, J. (2014). Plastic pollution in the world's oceans: More than 5 trillion plastic pieces weighing over 250,000 tons afloat at sea. *PLOS ONE*, 9(12), e111913. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0111913>
- Haque, M. R., Ali, M. M., Ahmed, W., Siddique, M. A. B., Akbor, M. A., Islam, M. S., & Rahman, M. M. (2023). Assessment of microplastics pollution in aquatic species (fish, crab, and snail), water, and sediment from the Buriganga River, Bangladesh: An ecological risk appraisal. *Science of The Total Environment*, 857(Part 1), 159344. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.159344>
- Hassan, M. A., & Ibrahim, R. E. (2025). Microplastics in fish: A comprehensive review. *Egyptian Journal of Aquatic Biology and Fisheries*, 29(4), 2987–3007. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejabf.2025.2987-3007>

doi.org/10.21608/ejabf.2025.449308

- Hossain, M. B., Banik, P., Nur, A. U., & Rahman, T. (2023). Abundance and characteristics of microplastics in commercial marine fish from the Bay of Bengal. *Environmental Pollution*, 318, 120854.
- Hossain, M. B., Pingki, F. H., Azad, M. A. S., Nur, A.-A. U., Banik, P., Paray, B. A., Arai, T., & Yu, J. (2023). Microplastics in different tissues of a commonly consumed fish, *Scomberomorus guttatus*, from a large subtropical estuary: Accumulation, characterization, and contamination assessment. *Biology*, 12(11), 1422. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biology12111422>
- Hossain, M. S., Saifullah, A. S. M., Uddin, M. J., & Rahaman, M. H. (2024). Assessment of microplastics in coastal ecosystem of Bangladesh. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 285, 116622. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2024.116622>
- Hussain, M. G., & Hoq, M. E. (Eds.). (2010). Sustainable management of fisheries resources of the Bay of Bengal. Support to Sustainable Management of the BOBL ME Project, Bangladesh Fisheries Research Institute. SBOBLMEP Pub./Rep. 2.
- Islam, K. R., Debnath, P. C., Rahman, M. S., Chakraborty, T. K., Chowdhury, P., Netema, B. N., Nice, M. S., Rayhan, M. A., Hasan, M. J., Asif, S. M. H., Biswas, A., Sarker, S., Ahmmmed, M., Zaman, S., Ghosh, G. C., Hasibuzzaman, M., Rahman, I. M., & Islam, S. (2025). Tracing the journey of microplastics in the Northern Bay of Bengal marine ecosystems, Bangladesh: A comprehensive study on source appointments, distribution, and potential risks. *Journal of Hazardous Materials Advances*, 19, 100829. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hazadv.2025.100829>
- Islam, M. M., Rayhan, A. B. M. S., Wang, J., Shamim, M. A. H., Ke, H., Wang, C., Zheng, X., Chen, D., & Cai, M. (2025). Tracing microplastics in marine fish: Ecological threats and human exposure in the Bay of Bengal. *Science of The Total Environment*, 963, 178462. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2025.178462>
- Islam, T., Li, Y., Rob, M. M., & Cheng, H. (2022). Microplastic pollution in Bangladesh: Research and management needs. *Environmental Pollution*, 308, 119697. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2022.119697>
- Jolaosho, T. L., Rasaq, M. F., Omotoye, E. V., Araomo, O. V., Adekoya, O. S., Abolaji, O. Y., & Hungbo, J. J. (2025). Microplastics in freshwater and marine ecosystems: Occurrence, characterization, sources, distribution dynamics, fate, transport processes, potential mitigation strategies, and policy interventions. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 293, 118036. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2025.118036>
- Kühn, S., Van Oyen, A., Booth, A. M., Meijboom, A., & Van Franeker, J. A. (2018). Marine microplastic: Preparation of relevant test materials for

laboratory assessment of ecosystem impacts. *Chemosphere*, 213, 103-113

- Kushwaha, M., Shankar, S., Goel, D., Singh, S., Rahul, J., Rachna, K., & Singh, J. (2024). Microplastics pollution in the marine environment: A review of sources, impacts and mitigation. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 209 (Part A), 117109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2024.117109>
- Li, Y., Chen, L., Zhou, N., Chen, Y., Ling, Z., & Xiang, P. (2024). Microplastics in the human body: A comprehensive review of exposure, distribution, migration mechanisms, and toxicity. *Science of The Total Environment*, 946, 174215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.174215>
- Lithner, D., Larsson, Å., & Dave, G. (2011). Environmental and health hazard ranking and assessment of plastic polymers based on chemical composition. *Science of the Total Environment*, 409(18), 3309–3324. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2011.04.038>
- Lusher, A. L., McHugh, M., & Thompson, R. C. (2013). Occurrence of microplastics in the gastrointestinal tract of pelagic and demersal fish from the English Channel. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 67, 94–99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2012.11.028>
- Masura, J., Baker, J., Foster, G., & Arthur, C. (2015). Laboratory methods for the analysis of microplastics in the marine environment (NOAA Technical Memorandum NOS-OR&R-48, July). NOAA Marine Debris Program. https://marinedebris.noaa.gov/sites/default/files/publications_files/noaa_microplastics_methods_manual.pdf
- Pan, Z., Zhang, C., Wang, S., Sun, D., Zhou, A., Xie, S., Xu, G., & Zou, J. (2021). Occurrence of microplastics in the gastrointestinal tract and gills of fish from Guangdong, South China. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 9(9), 981. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse9090981>
- Parvin, F., Nath, B., & Sultana, N. (2022). Abundance and characteristics of microplastics in commercial fish from the Kuakata beach of the Bay of Bengal. *Journal of Environmental Science and Health*, 57(11), 945-955.
- Peng, X., Chen, M., Chen, S., Dasgupta, S., Xu, H., Ta, K., Du, M., Li, J., Guo, Z., Bai, S. (2018). Microplastics contaminate the deepest part of the world's ocean. *Geochem. Persp. Let.* 9, 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.7185/geochemlet.1829>
- Rahman, M., Hoque, M. E., Hasan, Z., Alam, M. M. T., Jakaria, M., Das, K., Rangel-Buitrago, N., & Siddique, M. A. M. (2025). Quantification and characterization of microplastics in an intertidal gastropod the common periwinkle *Littorina littorea*. *Water Biology and Security*, 4(4), 100401. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watbs.2025.100401>
- Rochman, C. M., Hoh, E., Hentschel, B. T., & Kaye, S. (2013). Long-term field measurement of sorption of organic contaminants to five types of plastic

pellets: Implications for plastic marine debris. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 47(3),1646–1654. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es303700s>

- Siddique, M. A. M., Das, K., Shazada, N. E., & Walker, T. R. (2025). Microplastic ingestion and potential risk assessment on commercial and non-commercial marine fish in the Bay of Bengal. *Water, Air, & Soil Pollution*, 236(2), 83. doi. <https://org/10.1007/s11270-024-07719-9>
- Silva, R. D., Santos, P. H., Oliveira, G. F., & Almeida, L. C. (2023). Characterization of PS/PP/HDPE/LDPE polymer blend obtained from plastic waste collected on beaches in Ilhéus-Bahia, Brazil. *Polymers*, 15(20),4155. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym15204155>
- Srisiri, S., Haetrakul, T., Dunbar, S. G., & Chansue, N. (2024). Microplastic contamination in edible marine fishes from the upper Gulf of Thailand. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 198, 115785. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbu-l.2023.115785>
- Su, L., Xue, Y., Li, L., Yang, D., Kolandhasamy, P., Li, D., & Shi, H. (2019). Microplastics in Taihu Lake, China: Field observations and removal by microalgae. *Environmental Pollution*, 216, 711–719. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.en.008vpol2016.06>
- Sultana, S., Anisuzzaman, M., Hossain, M. K., Rana, M. S., Paray, B. A., Arai, T., Yu, J., & Hossain, M. B. (2024). Ecological risk assessment of microplastics and mesoplastics in six common fishes from the Bay of Bengal coast. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 204, 116544. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2024.116544>
- Tamang, G. L., Adhikari, B., Shrestha, M., Pradhananga, A. R., Shakya, B. D., Pant, D. R., Shakya, R. K., Maharjan, J., Shakya, S., & Shakya, P. R. (2023). Bioaccumulation and health risk assessment of heavy metals in some fish species available in local fish markets of Kathmandu, Nepal. *International Journal of Applied Sciences and Biotechnology*, 11(2), 85-98. <https://doi.org/10.3126/ijasbt.v11i2.56121>
- Tamim, A. R., Harun, M. A. Y. A., Islam, M. A., Bahar, M. M., Islam, M. S., & Hasan, M. (2025). Microplastic contamination in vertical water columns and fish: A comparative study between the Buriganga River and the Bay of Bengal in Bangladesh. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 197, 851. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-025-14328-4>
- Toha, M., Sikder, S., Rahman, M. M., & Muhib, M. I. (2024). Microplastic Occurrences in Freshwater Fish of Bangladesh. In I. M. M. Rahman & Z. A. Begum (Eds.), *Pollution Annual Volume 2024*. Intech Open. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.114897>
- Uhrin, A. V., Kershaw, P. J., Uhrin, A., & Lusher, A. (2019). GESAMP 2019 guidelines for the monitoring and assessment of plastic litter in the ocean (Reports & Studies No. 99). Joint Group of Experts on the Scientific Aspects of Marine Environmental Protection (GESAMP).

- Walkinshaw, C., Lindeque, P. K., Thompson, R., Tolhurst, T., & Cole, M. (2020). Microplastics and seafood: Lower trophic organisms at highest risk of contamination. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 190, 110066. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2019.110066>
- Worm, B., Lotze, H. K., Jubinville, I., Wilcox, C., & Jambeck, J. (2017). Plastic as a persistent marine pollutant. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 42, 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-102016-060700>
- Xu, P., Peng, G., Su, L., Gao, Y., Gao, L., & Li, D. (2018). Microplastic risk assessment in surface waters: A case study in the Changjiang Estuary, China. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 133(June), 647–654. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2018.06.020>
- Yarahmadi, A., Heidari, S. M., Sepahvand, P., Afkhami, H., & Kheradjoo, H. (2024). Microplastics and environmental effects: Investigating the effects of microplastics on aquatic habitats and their impact on human health. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 12, 1411389. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2024.1411389>
- Yona, D., Maharani, M. D., Cordova, M. R., Elvania, Y., & Dharmawan I. W. E. (2020). Microplastics analysis in the gill and gastrointestinal tract of coral reef fishes from three small outer islands of papua, indonesia: a preliminary study. *Jurnal Ilmu Dan Teknologi Kelautan Tropis*, 12(2), 495-505. <https://doi.org/10.29244/jitkt.v12i2.25971>
- Yousuf, A. H. M., Alim Shampa, M. T., Hasan Rifat, M. N., & Habib, S. (2025). Microplastics in the Bay of Bengal: A critical review of bioaccumulation and ecological impacts across Bangladesh. *Journal of Sea Research*, 208, 102615. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seares.2025.102615>
- Zaman, F., Rahman, M. A., Haque, M. M., Akbor, M. A., & Tareq, S. M. (2024). Pervasiveness and classification of microplastics in landfill leachate: Impacts, risks, and treatment efficiency. *Journal of Hazardous Advances*, 16, 100502. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hazadv.2024.100502>

